

Aligning University Communication Curricula with Digital Market Demands in Ecuador, South America

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Abstract

Background: As digital competencies become essential for labour market integration, universities must continuously adapt their curricula to prevent a disconnect between academic training and industry demands.

Objective: This study evaluates the perceptions of students, alumni, industry experts, and youth leaders regarding the modernisation of communication education—specifically in strategic and transmedia communication—at the Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja, Ecuador, within its distance and online learning modalities.

Methodology: A mixed-methods approach was employed, utilising surveys for students and alumni alongside semi-structured interviews with experts and youth leaders. Data were collected between January and March 2025 using non-probability convenience sampling via a "snowball" distribution dynamic. The study incorporated a content analysis of existing curricula and a longitudinal comparison with 2021 data to identify evolving academic interests.

Results: Findings identify digital communication, social media, transmedia, marketing, and organisational communication as critical areas for reinforcement. Alumni noted a significant gap between theoretical training and professional practice. Students identified digital media production, marketing, and sustainability-focused communication as the most promising career sectors. Experts highlighted the absence of local transmedia benchmarks in Ecuador, suggesting an opportunity to develop new communication logics. Meanwhile, youth leaders

emphasised the high consumption of social media while affirming the professional value of communication.

Conclusion: The study underscores an urgent need for practical training through organisational partnerships, media engagement, and entrepreneurship. It concludes that student preferences have shifted toward transmedia and strategic communication, with an apparent demand for applied, rather than purely theoretical, pedagogical models.

Unique Contribution: This research provides a roadmap for curriculum reform in emerging communication fields. It advocates integrating Big Data, Artificial Intelligence, and ethical frameworks into future academic offerings to ensure that graduates are equipped to navigate the complexities of the global digital economy.

Keywords: communication students, curricula, strategic communication, transmedia narratives, university education

Introduction

The transition to digital communication presents opportunities and risks, provided that it seeks to preserve the characteristics of participatory, multimedia, and interactive journalism (García-Avilés & Arias, 2016). As the first quarter of the 21st century approaches, and with the widespread adoption of mobile phones, a large proportion of the population can generate and consume communication content, at the expense of declining consumption of traditional media. An example of this is television, which is experiencing a decrease in subscribers; “according to estimates by Digital TV Research, the number of Latin Americans with access to a paid television service is expected to decrease from 72 million subscribers in 2017 to 67 million in 2025” (Olavarria et al., 2021, p. 27). Media such as print newspapers and magazines have shifted from print to digital platforms, turning journalists into multitaskers (Arriaga, 2017), while radio stations have turned to podcasting (Barrios-Rubio & Reyes-Espitia, 2023).

This transformation also poses challenges for professionals and educational systems, since “it seems clear that new subjects and skills will have to be incorporated, such as [...] data analytics, infographics, data journalism, distribution through social networks, new audiovisual formats, content marketing, etc.” (Sáez, 2020, p. 146). The digital field requires competencies that academic programs must incorporate; otherwise, graduates of communication programs risk becoming outdated and having little chance of securing employment (Martínez, 2023).

The academy's response is to move towards a “mixed transversality” in the sense of integrating the profile demanded by the cybermedia with the classic degrees (Tejedor, 2006), so that the treatment of big data, the use of technological tools and hypermedia narratives are in a new profile where “software, statistics and database management take the lead” (López, et al., 2016, p. 292). Another piece of evidence that encourages the review of training programmers is that “currently, job offers in communications related to data analysis, programming, design, or digital creativity are not covered. To address these areas, the future journalist needs interdisciplinary training” (Saavedra et al., 2020, p. 106).

In the search for a balance between classical, fundamental knowledge and the new demands of the digital space, a dilemma arises regarding the role of the university. It is expected from “academic institutions an important reflection and a wide flexibility to adapt their curricular

offer and their methodologies to the demands of the new communicative scenario” (Ufarte, et al., 2020, p.142), without neglecting the teaching of language and writing. They should focus their efforts on specialising students “in specific areas, in order to mark a competitive advantage over other related professionals” (Villanueva et al., 2018, p. 201). As a vocational career, it reaffirms that companies require a high level of commitment from students and communication professionals, encompassing all activities related to journalism and audiovisual production.

Even with the changes, it will be necessary to continue preparing students “for a tough sector whose precariousness is worsening [...] which allows for greater job flexibility and, at the same time, exposes informants to a greater risk of precariousness” (Marín-Sanchiz & González-Esteban, 2021, p. 575). Therefore, it is appropriate to train in competencies that lead to association and teamwork, to identify the logics of the emerging model of entrepreneurship and temporary mobilities characteristic, for example, in audiovisual production today, mediated by artificial intelligence, with which 60% of communication students from various Ecuadorian universities indicate they are very familiar (Duque & Puertas, 2024).

The situation of journalists and the media in Ecuador is no different from the above. On the one hand, digital media have already incorporated interfaces and interactive applications for digital users (Aguirre & Odriozola, 2017). On the other hand, there is a gap between university training and the requirements of companies: “the level of knowledge perceived by managers is [of] greater strength in theoretical and conceptual aspects, but with a weakness in the practical component” (Trámpuz et al., 2019, p. 20).

In the scenario described above, a proposal emerged at the Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja (UTPL) in Ecuador to meet the emerging demands of the communication industries and the aspirations of young people. This institutional intention was anticipated in the “UTPL 2032 Prospective Study” by the Department of Communication Sciences, which proposed the creation of new undergraduate and postgraduate programmes linked to the country's social problems. Furthermore, the prospective study on the creation of degree programmes concludes, among other points, that students should be equipped with skills in using tools and artificial intelligence (Yaguana et al., 2023).

Offering a degree in transmedia and strategic communication is justified by the evolution of the communication landscape, online media production, and strategic management in organisations (Baquerizo-Neira et al., 2024). It should be noted that the aforementioned studies provide an essential theoretical framework that justifies the updating of university communication curricula. The research by López-García et al. (2017) identifies emerging professional profiles and requisite technological skills, while García-Avilés and Arias (2016) document the transition to digital media. Studies conducted in Ecuador (Aguirre & Odriozola, 2017; Trámpuz et al., 2019) also confirm the existence of a gap between university education and labour-market demands. On the other hand, the literature on transmedia narratives (Scolari, 2013) and data journalism (Saavedra et al., 2020) supports the need to incorporate these emerging specialities into contemporary academic programmes, especially in the context of digital transformation in communication.

Objective

The objective is to identify perspectives for future studies on communication among students, professionals, and media managers to determine opportunities for education in Ecuador. The case study focuses on students and graduates of the distance learning and online communication programme at UTPL in Ecuador. The rationale for considering distance-learning students is that they live in different cities across the country and learn through a model that democratises access to education; this mechanism respects and values people's cultures and identities and is reinforced by virtuality. The research question is: Is it justified to update the academic curriculum in communication studies to encompass emerging trends in transmedia and strategic communication?

Materials and methods

The research is descriptive and relational (Hernández et al., 2000), using qualitative and quantitative methodology through surveys and semi-structured interviews. All surveys were administered to convenience non-probability samples based on participant availability and were completed by the researchers. Students and alumni of UTPL's Communication degree program completed surveys via Google Forms and were asked to provide their opinions on the studies and suggestions for improvement. The variables for the 2021 and 2025 surveys were derived from the conclusions of López-García et al. (2017) on the professional profiles of journalists. Data processing was carried out using SPSS (version 22).

The first survey, distributed in a “snowball” dynamic, was carried out between 3 and 28 February 2025 and was aimed at communication graduates. Fifty-two respondents living in various cities in Ecuador and two in Madrid, where there is an academic office of the UTPL. The average number of years worked by the respondents is 10, of whom 14 (27%) work as employees in companies; 12 (23%) are entrepreneurs or self-employed; 11 (21%) are educators in both the private and public sector in schools, high schools or universities; 8 (15%) are employed in the public sector; 3 (6%) are journalists and 4 (8%) do not work. The second survey was applied between 4 and 17 February 2025. Sixty-seven communication students from UTPL who live in different cities in Ecuador participated in the survey; 49 were working, and 18 were not at the time of the survey. The average age is 27 years old. The participants are from private schools (30 participants) and public schools (37 participants).

The interviews with experts and youth leaders were conducted between January and March 2025, via telephone and videoconference. The interviewee profiles correspond to Interviewee 1 (E1). Journalist with 30 years of professional experience, graduated in communication with a specialisation in political communication, media director, and trainer. Interviewee 2 (E2). Immersive, interactive and multiplatform storyteller. Co-founder and creative director at Imán Transmedia. Professor in postgraduate programmes. Interviewee 3 (E3). University research professor. Leader of a research group on communication, transmedia, and gamification. Leader 1 (L1), female, 16 years old, high school student, lives in Quito. Leader 2 (L2), male, 17 years old, high school student, lives in Quito. Leader 3 (L3), male, 19 years old, high school student, lives in Quito.

A content analysis was also conducted of the academic curricula of national and international universities that offer programs similar to transmedia and strategic communication. Using Google searches and the SCImago Institutions Rankings, 13 names were identified, including those associated with UTPL.

To understand the evolution of students' interests, the data are contrasted with information collected in 2021 through a survey and semi-structured interviews. The survey was conducted between 13 and 22 July 2021 and included 110 students residing in various cities in Ecuador. The reliability of the survey, in the questions about the competencies that a communicator should possess (Likert scale answers), was evaluated through the Cronbach's Alpha statistic for 11 items, with a result of 0.86 which implies a good or high level of confidence (Frías-Navarro, 2020); this implies that researchers can use the instrument to collect information and trust the results. The participant profiles are: 60 women (54.5%) and 50 men (45.5%); marital status: single, 81.8%; married or in a couple, 14.5%; divorced or separated, 3.7%.

The semi-structured interviews were conducted from 14 to 22 July 2021 with journalists, media managers and experts living in 11 cities in Ecuador. The characteristics of the interviewees are: 13 men and seven women, of whom seven are related to radio, one to television, two to social media, two to public administration, three to print media, two to teaching, and three in free professional practice. The average age is 44 years old. The testimonies are identified using the following coding: E-00 (interviewee and interview number).

Results

The relevant results of the first survey of communication graduates indicate that the fields of knowledge that should receive greater emphasis are digital communication and social networks (37% of respondents); transmedia narratives (29%); organisational communication strategies (19%); and other areas (15%). This selection is related to skills and perceptions of future job opportunities. The skills most in demand by employers are handling AI tools (52% of respondents), creating transmedia content (27%), developing narrative strategies (12%), and other reasons (9%). Future job opportunities will be in sectors such as content production for digital platforms (53%), data management and audience analysis (33%), and sustainability-related consultancy (14%).

The training received by graduates was excessively theoretical (58% of respondents); only one in three (31%) reported a balance between theory and practice, while 11% indicated that they received more practical training than theoretical. For future offers, it is advisable to seek a balance between theoretical and practical content (40%), although the curriculum tends to favour practical training (37%). The most beneficial professional internships are those in private companies (42%), in the creation of their own enterprises (23%), in the development of multi- and transmedia projects (21%), and other types of internships (14%). On the other hand, for 85% of the participants, it is moderately important to include training on entrepreneurship, and this training includes topics on innovation in business models (50% of respondents), marketing strategies (27%), resource management and finance (21%) and other subjects (2%).

As a result of the second survey, applied to communication students, it is known that the contents that should be increased or strengthened in the current curriculum are digital marketing (34%), transmedia and strategic communication (30%), graphic design and multimedia (24%), and others (12%). Students who have the possibility of switching to a new academic offer related to transmedia and strategic communication would do so in order to improve their skills (70% of respondents); they hope to manage emerging technologies in digital media (33%), manage sustainable ventures in communication (25%) and provide strategic communication services in organisations (24%). Thus, the distinguishing

characteristics of a new career are its link to real projects (54%), the methodology applied (24%), flexibility in class schedules (20%), and other factors (2%). According to the students, the most promising sectors to work in are audiovisual production for digital media (37%), digital marketing (25%), communication related to sustainability (21%), and others (17%).

For the experts, in Ecuador “there are still no points of reference as in other countries on the development of transmedia, not only from a theoretical point of view, but also in practice” E3, so “I think that by addressing transmedial communication we could find ways to awaken interest in students and generate new communication logics” E2, through “a training process that combines communication with the part of entrepreneurship, which is a business, not only from the news genre but also entertainment, sports, and advertising with digital strategic communication tools to make a strategic plan” E1. “It is clear that digital communication is going to displace traditional communication. I am convinced that radio is not going to die, but digital communication is going to have a superlative importance” E1. Furthermore, “in the next few years we will have spatial computing devices that will allow virtual elements in physical environments, putting on glasses, and that will affect how we are going to think about our content” E2, therefore, “it is necessary to know what is being done in the field of transmedia” E3.

“Today it would seem that AI is the basis of transmedia. From the technical point of view, it facilitates production, but, although it is incipient, there is a lack of immersive experiences that generate interaction options” E3. From this reflection, it is pointed out that, “I don't think there are specific proposals on transmedia as such [...] within a career it will generate curiosity, because it feeds the student's spirit” E2, but in any scenario, “artificial intelligence and emerging technologies will be seen in five years” time with much more power” E3. Experts point out that “creating a business model is something that we communicators don't have in our heads. And we hit the rock when we realise that we have to monetise” E2, so “promoting digital entrepreneurship would involve combining intellectual training with entrepreneurial skills. I think it's interesting because today journalists don't find space in the traditional media” E1.

In another vein, the testimonies of the youth leaders focus on the use and consumption of social networks but highlight the value of communication as a profession. “Own a TikTok channel; I upload content depending on where I go. It is essential to teach about social networks because they require professionalism. That is a vision I have, networks are communication” L2. “A career in communication is important because of the influence on the masses, for example, Martin Luther King and Hitler had incredible speeches, and used them for different things. Then, communication is power” L3. The case of an opinion leader in social networks is cited, “the influencer Bocha Deportes talks about the potential that Ecuador has. It appeals to me. Maybe in five years, there will be more people who develop in this, who have their own main content and reach more people,” L1.

The content analysis identified three areas—academic, scientific, and professional—to inform the future design of educational offerings related to the interests expressed by students, graduates, and experts, as identified in both the surveys and the interviews.

Table 1 presents the results for the main variables of the general information, media, and training dimensions of the survey administered in 2021, to assess trends relative to the current

data. There is a concentration in the younger age ranges, which corresponds to the group of respondents who answered the form: distance learners. The most preferred media are digital and traditional radio. The most popular degree titles are social communication, journalism, digital communication and social networks. The areas or workplaces where students expect to work are classified as public or private, i.e., as civil service positions; their preferences for online and traditional media are then ranked.

Table 1. Relations between media and training

Ages	Preferred media						Total
	News Agency	Internet Media / Streaming	Paper newspapers and magazines	Traditional radio	Cable TV / Satellite TV	No preferences	
17-27	5	61	1	2	4	2	75
28-38	1	14	2	5	2	1	25
39-49	0	1	0	2	0	2	5
50-60	0	2	0	1	0	0	3
61-71	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
72 and more	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Total	6	80	3	10	6	5	110

Ages	Attractive degree. Bachelor's degree in communication...						Total
	Digital communication and social	Organisational communication	Social communication	Audiovisual and multimedia communication	Journalism	Digital journalism and	
17-27	14	4	20	17	16	4	75
28-38	7	4	8	1	4	1	25
39-49	2	0	0	1	2	0	5
50-60	1	0	0	0	1	1	3

61-71	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
72 and more	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Total	24	9	28	19	24	6	110
Preferred area of work							Total
Ages	Traditional press, radio and TV	Civil servant (public or private sector)	Consultancy / self-employment	Teaching	Online media / social networks	Other*	
17-27	6	30	3	4	28	4	75
28-38	3	7	5	2	6	2	25
39-49	1	3	0	0	1	0	5
50-60	0	1	1	0	1	0	3
61-71	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
72 and more	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total	11	42	9	6	36	6	110

*Other: sports journalism, photography, investigative journalism

A relationship was sought between degree title preferences and career areas (Table 2). According to the Chi-Square test, the asymptotic significance (bilateral) is 0.003 less than 0.05; therefore, the null hypothesis that the variables “preferred areas of work” and “attractive degree title” are independent is rejected. On the contrary, there is an association between the variables. The degrees students pursue align with the areas or places where they aspire to work. Those who aim for a degree in social communication expect to become civil servants. In contrast, those who select degrees in digital communication, audiovisual, and multimedia report a preference for working in online media.

Table 2. Association between degree and employment

Attractive Bachelor's communication... degree in	Preferred areas of work						Total
	Traditional press, radio and TV	Civil servant (public or private sector)	Consultancy / self-employment	Teaching	Online media / social networks	Other*	

Digital communication and social	1	4	2	1	15	1	24
Organisational communication	0	6	2	0	0	1	9
Social communication	2	16	2	2	6	0	28
Audiovisual and multimedia communication	2	6	0	1	9	1	19
Journalism	6	7	1	1	6	3	24
Digital journalism and data analysis	0	3	2	1	0	0	6
Total	11	42	9	6	36	6	110

*Other: sports journalism, photography, investigative journalism.

Another research instrument applied in 2021 is semi-structured interviews. These allowed us to identify challenges that communicators face in the transition to digital media, particularly notable: 1) Verification. 2) Learning and implementing communication technologies. 3) Funding for training.

Discussion and conclusions

Between 2021 and 2025, students' preferences regarding perceptions of future employment changed. In 2021, the majority of students had no intention of pursuing a career related to new forms of communication, and their job expectations were to work as civil servants. Today, the majority seek to learn about digital communication, transmedia, and new narratives, and job preferences are oriented toward roles as entrepreneurs, freelancers, or consultants, specifically in content generation on digital platforms and data management. This conclusion takes force based on the evidence found in the data in Table 1 (Chi-Square test) that points to the relationship between “preferred areas to work in” and “attractive career title”.

However, there is continuity in the content expected to be strengthened. In 2021 and 2025, students requested the inclusion of content on digital communication and social networks, computer science, skills for mass forms of online communication, transmedia narratives, and organisational communication strategies in academic programmes. According to graduates of the degree, preferences that align with the competences demanded by employers include knowledge of transmedia communication applied to organisations. Among the main challenges that Ecuador's communicators perceive in the transition to digital media are the misinformation that spreads on the Internet, the continuous learning of new forms and technologies of communication, the search for funding to cover the training and continuing education they need in an environment of good relations with government entities, and lobbying for the promotion of public policies in communication.

The impression of those interviewed in 2021 is that the implementation of communication technologies can be an opportunity to streamline data processing and address misinformation, but computers will not replace people. Fieldwork, dialogues, culture, and emotions would not be changed by robots that lack feelings. There are protocols and automated mechanisms that already support rapid updates among communication professionals, without sacrificing a humanistic horizon. For the experts consulted, in 2025, there is an opportunity to meet the expectations of the industry. Of young people through training in transmedia and strategic

communication that enables them to found companies, and it is also necessary to embrace the trend of incorporating AI into the management and generation of multi-, cross-, and transmedia content. This means nurturing youth concerns that are awakened by emerging communication platforms and formats. In the opinion of the youth leaders consulted, it is essential to learn about social media because communication will always have the power to influence the masses.

In 2021, students indicated that their degree programme should retain its current name, although more than half of respondents preferred alternative emphases, including digital and data communication. However, in 2025, there is broad acceptance of a shift toward transmedia and strategic communication, driven by the development of skills in emerging technologies, the management of ventures, and the meeting of organisational expectations. This reading is related to the information presented by the UTPL's General Directorate of Liaison with Society (M. Landacay, personal communication, February 26, 2025), when it conducted a follow-up survey of communication graduates from the 2018 to 2021 study periods, to characterise and enhance the university's continuous improvement processes as inputs for relevance studies and improvements in the graduate profile.

The results reflect a dialectical tension between traditional humanistic education and new technological demands, confirming Tejedor's (2006) predictions about the need for “mixed transversality” in communication. Students' preference for transmedia and strategic communication corroborates Scolari's (2013) thesis, while the demand for skills in generative artificial intelligence and big data confirms the findings of López-García et al. (2017) on new professional profiles, which is also in line with international trends to integrate AI into communication training programmes, such as in Australian and Turkish universities (Imran, 2025). However, although graduates perceive their training as overly theoretical, experts suggest maintaining a humanistic perspective. This dialectic proposes that the challenge lies not in incorporating technology but in achieving a balanced synthesis that preserves the critical and ethical essence of communication.

Based on the results, the research question is answered affirmatively. Yes, an update to the academic offer of university studies in communication is justified to align with emerging trends in transmedia and strategic communication. At the same time, new lines of research emerge to examine the application of new curricula, their articulation with the goals of sustainable development, and the evolution of automation, immersive narratives, and entrepreneurship in digital ecosystems in Ecuador and across the region.

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